

NOTES

Manganese(II) Complexes of Some Oximes

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THE present paper describes preparation and characterization of Mn(II) complexes of some orthohydroxyaldoximes, viz.,

- (i) salicylaldehyde (salH₂) and (ii) *o*-vanillin-oxime (vanH₂)

salH₂

vanH₂

Bis-chelates having square-planar geometry around Mn(II) with rare spin state $S=3/2$ are obtained with both the ligands.

Experimental

- (a) *Preparation of complexes* :

Ethanol solution of ligands and aqueous solution of manganese(II) acetate were mixed together keeping the metal ligand ratio as 1 : 2. In case of *o*-vanillin-oxime sodium acetate solution was added dropwise until a green coloured complex was separated out. In the case of salicylaldehyde sodium hydroxide solution had to be added dropwise until a dark green coloured complex precipitated out. The complexes were filtered out, washed with water. It was then recrystallized from ethanol and dried in an electric oven at $\sim 60^\circ$.

The complexes are insoluble in water and soluble in all the common organic solvents. Elemental analysis data are given in Table 1.

- (b) *Physical measurements* :

Magnetic susceptibility measurements on the solid complexes were made at room temperature by the Gouy method using mercury tetrathiocyanatocobaltate(II) as calibrating agent ($\chi_g = 16.44 \times 10^{-6}$ cgs units). ESR spectra were recorded on Varian E₂-EPR spectrophotometer, operating at about ~ 9.4 GHz with 100 KHz field modulation and phase sensitive detection.

Results and Discussion

Both the complexes have the composition Mn(ligand-H)₂. *Bis*-chelates of salicylaldehyde are known to attain planar geometry deriving extrastability from the additional rings formed through hydrogen bonding¹⁻³. A similar structure (I) may, therefore, be considered for the complexes under discussion.

(I) X = H, 3-OCH₃

Because of the complicated pattern of the splitting⁴ of the d-orbitals in planar complexes, 4-coordinate planar manganese(II) complexes may involve three different types of spin pairing leading to give five ($b_{2g}^1, e_g^2, a_{1g}^1, b_{1g}^1$), three ($b_{2g}^2, e_g^2, a_{1g}^1$) and one (b_{2g}^2, e_g^3) unpaired electrons for a d^5 case.

The two complexes show room temperature magnetic moments of 4.51 and 4.35 BM respectively (Table 1). Full spin pairing is thus readily excluded. If the spin free configuration i.e., $S=5/2$ is considered, the lowering from $\mu_{s.o.}$ (5.92 BM) may have to be attributed to antiferromagnetic interaction. But the results of magnetic susceptibility measurements in solution do not confirm to this proposition. Partial spin pairing i.e., $S=3/2$ appears to be the best choice. The experimental values of 4.51 and 4.35 BM as against the spin-only value of 3.87 BM may be interpreted in terms of orbital contribution introduced by spin-orbit coupling.

Solutions of the complexes in ethanol show magnetic moments of 4.55 and 4.20 BM respectively (Table 1). The values are quite close to those obtained for the solid complexes. This excludes an alternative explanation of the magnetic moment data

TABLE 1—COLOUR, COMPOSITION, MAGNETIC MOMENTS AND g-VALUES OF THE COMPLEXES

Complex	Colour	Elemental analysis Found (Calcd)				μ_{eff} (BM)			g-value
		Mn%	O%	H%	N%	Solid	Ethanol	Pyridine	
Mn(salH) ₂	Dark green	15.9 (16.0)	51.6 (51.8)	3.60 (3.70)	8.20 (8.64)	4.51	4.55	5.73	2.00
Mn(hmbH) ₂	Light green	13.8 (13.5)	50.2 (50.0)	4.29 (4.16)	7.09 (7.29)	4.35	4.23	5.95	2.00

based on intermolecular antiferromagnetic interaction for $S=5/2$. In pyridine solution, however, the magnetic moments are raised to 5.7 and 5.9 BM respectively, which is suggestive of axial coordination by pyridine molecules.

Considerable work has been done on ESR spectra of Mn(II) complexes of $S=5/2$, but reports on those of $S=3/2$ are scanty^{5,6}. Probably the first ESR report on a Mn(II) complex of quartet ground state ($S=3/2$) is that on Mn(II) phthalocyanine⁷, polycrystalline sample of which at room temperature gives a broad signal centered around $g=2.00$. The complexes under discussion also give similar ESR spectra for polycrystalline samples (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. ESR Spectra (Polycrystalline, 300°K)
(a) Mn(salH)₂
(b) Mn(vanH)₂

The g-values of 2.00 indicate that there is little orbital contribution. This conclusion is in contradiction to that arrived at from the magnetic moment values, which are sufficiently larger than the μ spin-only value (3.88) and call for the orbital contribution. This enigma remains unexplained even for the much studied $S=3/2$ complex Mn(II)-phthalocyanine.

ESR spectra of the complexes have also been recorded for their solutions in benzene, chloroform,

ethanol and pyridine. Extremely broad, almost vanishing ESR signals are observed in all the cases, due possibly to zero field splitting interaction associated with the noncubic field in the complexes⁷⁻¹⁴.

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